

Pt Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara's Business Meeting Planning

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Abstract:- Meetings are an important medium for corporate organizations to provide and obtain information to each other, unite thoughts between employees, improve communication, encourage communication, and advance success within the organization. In its implementation, business meetings often run ineffectively. There are three stages to making an effective meeting, namely (1) Meeting preparation/planning (2) Meeting implementation (3) Post-meeting implementation/evaluation. This research will discuss how the planning stages of company business meetings are effective, so that the company can achieve the expected goals. This research is a qualitative descriptive research with data collection methods using interviews, observation and documentation. The research results obtained are that at the planning stage for an effective business meeting, there are several steps that must be ensured, including goal setting, program preparation, method testing or simulation, as well as communication and outreach to the parties involved.

Keywords:- Meetings, Meeting Methods, Effective Meetings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Post-pandemic developments in the digital economy and technology have influenced and brought long-term changes to various aspects in Indonesia, including business aspects. One clear proof of the role of technology in driving change in Indonesia is proven by the evolution of entrepreneurship that relies on technology in the digital era or what is usually called digital transformation (Nirwan & Dwanto, 2015). This is marked by an increase in the number of start-up companies since the first quarter of 2015, making Indonesia one of the countries most highlighted for its development (Noviandari, 2015). A startup or start-up company is a company run by at least 20 employees, where the business process moves digitally and has rapid movement (Suwarno & Silvianita, 2016).

Based on data from Startup Ranking, Indonesia has 2,492 startup companies as of June 14 2023. This number puts Indonesia in sixth place with the most startup companies in the world, beating Germany and France. It cannot be denied that the increasingly competitive conditions of the startup ecosystem and dynamic changes in global conditions require corporate organizations, especially startup companies, to continue to make many adjustments from time to time as the environment develops (Faria et al., 2021). In the dynamic climate of startup companies, companies are often faced with various challenges, one of which is the challenge of being able to adapt quickly to unexpected

market changes. In a dynamic startup climate like this, it is important for startup companies to have a good communication and coordination system. This communication and coordination system is often expressed through a forum for meetings between employees called meetings (Azlina, 2021).

Meetings are an important medium for corporate organizations to provide and obtain information to each other, unite thoughts between employees, improve communication, encourage communication, and advance success within the organization (Yusuf, 2020). The ultimate goal of holding a meeting is to establish communication between all meeting participants, have direct contributions from all meeting participants, and achieve problem resolution from the opinions expressed at the meeting (Behori & Alamin, 2018). Implementing good and effective meetings will result in better decision making, clearer planning, and more targeted follow-up, so that the realization of the company's strategic management can be more optimal and startup companies can achieve their long-term organizational goals (Sanrach & Silpjaru, 2020).

According to the results of a McKinsey survey published in May 2023, it showed that 61 global executives thought the meetings they attended were ineffective. In fact, only 37% of global executives feel that the meetings they attend produce productive and quality decisions. Meanwhile, as many as 80% of executives are considering or have implemented adaptive changes in effective meeting structures and methods as a response to the evolution of work systems used by companies post-pandemic. Apart from a survey from McKinsey, Harvard Business School also stated that 62% of executives considered that the meetings they attended did not succeed in increasing team cohesion because they were run poorly. Often, meeting leaders focus too much on preparing the technical aspects of preparing a meeting, such as location, food and equipment, without realizing that non-technical aspects also need to be considered (Azlina, 2021).

One of the startup companies that has managed to survive and develop from 2016 until now by having annual strategic meeting activities in its organizational system, is found at PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara. PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara is a local startup company

operating in industry *fast moving consumer goods* (FMCG). This company understands that in the dynamic world of startup business, it is important for startups to have a communication system that allows the exchange of information and fast and appropriate decision making. PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara believes that annual business meetings play a key role in communication, decision making and implementation of company strategy.

As a company that continues to grow, PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara understands that meetings are an important instrument in supporting coordination between divisions, making strategic decisions, and monitoring the implementation of business projects. PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara has taken various initiatives to ensure that their internal meetings run efficiently, effectively and support the achievement of company goals. This is marked by the holding of a business meeting at the end of each year which is called "*Strategic Planning Meeting*". Through this annual business meeting, it is hoped that PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara can evaluate their achievements over the past year, formulate new goals to be achieved in the coming period, and design strategies or innovations that will help them achieve company success in the future.

However, it can be said that this company's business meeting activities do not use effective methods. This data is strengthened by a pre-survey in the form of *quick interview* the writer with PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara, specifically with Mrs. Mirna Astari Magetsari, Vice President of the People and Culture division regarding the evaluation of the 2022 Work Meeting. Mrs. Mirna said that the previous year's meeting activities did not use a clear method, flow and structure so that lack of clear directions to participants. The method used at previous business meetings was only a lecture or presentation method (one-way method) from the founders, which made participants relatively bored and less active in meeting activities. This causes the aim of the business meeting itself to be able to produce output in the form of a new company strategy for the following year, which does not work as expected. Apart from the unclear flow, structure and methods used, the entire agenda of the previous year's business meeting was also only led by the founders who directed the course of the forum, which was a factor in participants not being able to freely express their opinions, there being hesitation in giving ideas to participants, and the absence of two-way discussions. direction between participants and the meeting leader.

The results of the pre-survey are in the form of data collection, *quick interview*, and the author's observations show that the main obstacles in organizing effective annual business meetings at PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara include the lack of human resources deployed in organizing these business meeting activities, from planning to evaluation. Based on the phenomena that have been described as well as an evaluation of the Rahsa Nusantara business meeting method in 2022, the author identifies several problems, including (1) PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara annual business meeting participants who are less active in meeting activities, (2) meeting participants get bored easily towards methods that are monotonous and only have a one-way nature, (3) unclear follow-up and company action plans after the meeting, and (4) lack of human resources on the part of the activity

organizer. Based on this phenomenon, the author will discuss "Planning Business Meetings at PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Meeting Concept

Meetings are activities that are often carried out by every company, be it daily, weekly, monthly or annual meetings with a specific purpose. There are a number of definitions regarding meetings according to experts, namely that meetings are reciprocal communication between two or more people to deepen a problem, reach an understanding, or decide on taking certain steps (Wibawa & Riyanto, 2018). Meanwhile, according to Paramita, a meeting is a means of gathering a group of people to unite their thoughts to discuss company affairs (Paramita, 2018). A meeting is a means of gathering a group of people to unite thoughts, considerations and opinions regarding an affair, problem or work with the hope of reaching an agreement, resolution and decision (Sampebu, 2020). Based on these expert opinions, it can be concluded that a meeting is a gathering of a group of individuals to unite opinions to find a solution to a problem in company activities. These meeting activities are carried out by people with interests for various purposes. Contains relevant literature or research. The method of writing sources in the text needs to clearly indicate the author's name and source citation, in the form of the year of publication and the page where the manuscript is located.

B. Meeting Function

The function of meetings in a company includes, among other things, to solve or find a way out of a problem or obstacle faced by the company. According to Purwatiangingsih and Pangemangan, obstacles are anything that can hinder a company from carrying out activities (Purwatiangingsih et al., 2018). When a company faces obstacles that can hinder its activities, meetings need to be held to find solutions related to the obstacles being faced. Apart from that, meetings also function as a good coordination tool between meeting participants and the company, accommodate all problems from meeting participants, convey information, orders and statements, and meetings can be used as a means of negotiation.

C. Effective Meetings

Effective meetings according to Jones (in Marianti, 2014) are "the planning, organizing, leading, and controlling of resources to achieve organizational goals effectively and efficiently" which means planning, organizing, controlling and leading resources to achieve goals. Effective meeting activities will enable meeting participants to not only know the meeting discussion (to know), not just memorize the meeting discussion (to memorize), but also enable meeting participants to understand, own and control (to understand) the results of the meeting discussion. which is carried out in accordance with the objectives of the meeting (Lumuan,

2014). There are several essential stages to holding an effective meeting. This stage will help make preparations for the meeting well organized, so that the meeting's goal of producing appropriate output can be achieved. These stages are (1) Meeting preparation/planning (2) Meeting implementation (3) Post-meeting implementation/evaluation. (Ultimate, 2015).

According to Marianti and Rebori, in meeting preparation or planning there are elements of 5W + 1H (Why, What, Who, When, Where, and How) (Mariani & Rebori, 2014).

➤ Why(Why)

Companies need to determine the reasons why the meeting needs to be held, why the meeting must be attended by participants, and why holding the meeting is important, so that the meeting can run in a directed manner, and both the meeting organizer and meeting participants both understand the urgency of why the meeting must be attended and are expected to be able to seriously participate in meeting activities. By knowing the reason for holding a meeting, the meeting's objectives can be more easily determined.

➤ What(What)

The company needs to know what is needed and needs to be prepared at the meeting, such as additional information, supporting data, meeting materials that need to be prepared such as presentations or reports, and the characteristics of the meeting participants. Apart from that, the estimated time or duration also needs to be considered and the meeting agenda must be clearly structured. Knowing what things must be considered in the meeting agenda and what things are needed at the meeting will be a guide for the meeting organizers and participants regarding the clarity of the structure, agenda, mechanisms and timing of the meeting can be well prepared, so that the meeting will run more effectively and the level of meeting success can be measured clearly. Apart from planning what needs to be prepared regarding the schedule of events, consumption and accommodation aspects also need to be considered. The consumption aspect concerns what food and drinks need to be prepared for meeting participants, such as snacks, coffee break consumption, and heavy meals for meeting participants. Meanwhile, the accommodation aspect concerns what is needed if the meeting is held outside the company, such as outside the city, which will require accommodation, travel transportation and lodging.

➤ Who(Who)

Companies need to know who will be involved in the meeting, including the meeting leader, speaker, moderator, note taker, meeting participants, and even people who help run the meeting. Meeting participants consist of people who are relevant and have an interest in the topic being discussed, such as company leaders, managers, team members, or parties related to the meeting. By knowing who will be involved, the meeting organizer can send invitations to these people, confirm attendance, and remind each component about the meeting. The invitation letter given to meeting participants will contain details of meeting activities such as the date and time of the meeting, the place where

the meeting will take place, and what topics will be discussed at the meeting.

➤ When(When)

Companies need to consider the most appropriate time to hold a meeting, starting from the date, day, and duration of the meeting. When determining the meeting schedule, consider the free time of the meeting participants, time availability, limitations of the participants, and the atmosphere of the day when the meeting is held so that all participants invited to the meeting can attend.

➤ Where(Where)

Companies need to consider where the meeting will be held, taking into account easy access, noise, the atmosphere of the place, the surrounding environment, and the facilities available at that place. In this point where, the place referred to is not only the building or location used, but also the preparation of the room used for the meeting, including adequate lighting and appropriate room temperature, room facilities such as audio-visual equipment, meeting table model, chair arrangement, boards, LCD projector, screen, loudspeaker (microphone), speakers, laptop, and other logistical tools that will influence the progress of the meeting so that meeting activities can run smoothly and as expected.

➤ How(How)

Next is how the meeting will be run, what stages of activities will be carried out during the meeting, and how the meeting agenda will be arranged. This includes how the meeting leader directs the course of the meeting, how to convey information, interact with participants, maintain meeting discipline, create the atmosphere as expected, how to maintain participant focus, facilitate open and participatory discussions, how to record follow-up decisions, and ensure how each participant is actively involved, including what meeting methods are used.

D. Meeting Method

According to Knowles in Farida, the meeting method is a way of organizing the audience to achieve a certain goal, which can also be interpreted as a method used by the meeting leader to build relationships with meeting participants during the meeting, a tool for creating the process of meeting activities, as well as presentation techniques. which is used by meeting leaders individually and in groups so that the information in the meeting can be absorbed, understood and carried out by meeting participants well (Farida, 2020). So, the meeting method can be interpreted as the method used to implement plans that have been prepared in the form of real and practical activities to achieve the meeting objectives.

In the entire process of holding a meeting, method is an important point that needs to be paid attention to because the success or failure of the meeting's objectives

depends on how the method used in the process of meeting activities that will be followed by the meeting participants is implemented (Hairunnisah, 2017). Achieving the goal of the meeting is one of the hopes and also becomes a guideline that will direct the process of running the meeting to achieve the company's goals as optimally as possible. One effort to achieve this goal is to use a method or a number of methods which will become techniques in holding meetings (Bararah, 2022). Meeting methods refer to certain approaches or methods used in planning, organizing and carrying out meeting activities. The methods used in meeting activities involve certain strategies to increase productivity, participation and decision making. This method depends on the goals to be achieved at the meeting.

The methods used to motivate participants to be able to bring out their best performance at work, foster good cooperation and collaboration between employees, solve a problem, and the methods used to make participants able to think and express their opinions in dealing with a problem will be different (Roestiyah, 2012, p. 1). According to Yunus in his book (Yunus, 2014), in the process of implementing the meeting method, there are three main stages in producing an effective meeting method, including planning, implementing and evaluating. According to Siagian (1994) in Yunus (Yunus, 2014), planning is the entire process of thinking and carefully determining the things that will be done in the future in order to achieve predetermined goals. According to Newman (in Firmansyah & Mahardhika, 2018, p. 35), planning is an activity to determine what will be done first, before implementing it later. In the context of effective method planning, there are several stages involved in helping to ensure that the planned process or activity can be carried out well and achieve the expected goals. The following are some general stages in planning an effective method:

➤ *Goal Setting*

Activities to identify and clearly determine the direction the company wants to achieve, both short, medium and long term. Having clear goals will help provide direction and provide a basis for further planning (Griffin in Sadikin et al., 2020, p. 22)

➤ *Situation Analysis*

Method planning requires situation analysis, namely a comprehensive analysis of the initial state or current situation, such as understanding the context, identifying needs, conveniences, and problems or challenges that will be faced. Situation analysis can help design methods that suit specific needs (Sawitri, 2015, p. 4)

➤ *Method Determination*

Based on the objectives and analysis that have been set, the next step is to choose the most appropriate method or approach by considering various factors. There are a number of factors in determining the method according to Hamdayama, namely: (a) the objectives to be achieved, (b) the circumstances or characteristics of the participants, (c) the discussion material, (d) the meeting situation, (e) the facilities available, (f) meeting leader, (g)

advantages and disadvantages of each method (Hamdayama, 2022).

➤ *Program Preparation*

The planning stage contains elements of preparing programs or planning activities in detail and concretely for each step or method that will be implemented. This arrangement includes the sequence of activities, time allocation, event structure, who and how will carry it out, as well as what facilities and equipment will be used to carry it out. (Yunus, 2014, p. 37)

➤ *Resource Preparation*

Preparation and allocation of required resources relating to budget, tools, equipment, place, facilities and people by taking into account efficiency and effectiveness. In a corporate organization, the resources owned are generally limited, so their use must be carefully arranged so that optimal results can be obtained (Yunus, 2014, p. 37).

➤ *Communication and Socialization Methods*

The planning stage also involves communication and outreach to the parties involved by explaining the information they need to know, such as the reasons for determining the method, objectives, benefits, and hopes so that the method planning can run effectively in accordance with the expected goals (Abidin, 2015, p. 155). Method planning needs to be communicated to all related parties so that all parties involved have the same understanding and agreement, so that in its implementation there will be no internal obstacles due to misunderstandings and disagreements (Yunus, 2014, p. 31).

➤ *Trial or Simulation Method*

Simulation is a means of imitating real events in some way for learning, testing, or training (Harrell in Ghosh, 2014). Trials or simulations are carried out to identify potential problems and ensure that all procedures and steps run smoothly according to what has been planned.

According to several experts, several meeting methods are commonly used, including brainstorming, presentations, lectures, discussions and role playing. The following is an explanation of each method.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a descriptive qualitative method, which is a research method usually used to examine the condition of natural objects, where the researcher acts as a key instrument in describing the situation objectively or based on visible facts Sugiyono (2018). Meanwhile, according to Margono in his book (Margono, 2003), the descriptive qualitative research method is a method that focuses on problems based on facts carried out by observation, interviews, and studying supporting documents or data. In descriptive qualitative research, careful verbal language needs to be considered because

all interpretations and conclusions drawn are conveyed verbally.

Based on these two opinions, it can be concluded that the descriptive qualitative research method is a method that does not only focus on observations, interviews or document analysis, but also involves the role of the writer as a key instrument for objectively describing the situation which will be conveyed verbally. This approach allows researchers to understand and describe phenomena more thoroughly, making it a suitable method for researching the natural and in-depth conditions of objects. This method was chosen in carrying out the project so that the author could obtain an overview in the field and implement the project objects at PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara optimally.

The research location in the form of planning activities will be carried out at the Rahsa Nusantara Office, Kampung Padi Housing, Jl. Cisituh Indah VI Block. F9, Dago, Coblong District, Bandung City, West Java 40135 on 16-18 November 2023. This research obtained primary and secondary data sources, with direct interviews with the company's main resource person, namely the Vice President of the People and Culture division Rahsa Nusantara as the person in charge of the project, participants at the PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara annual working meeting consisting of 11 participants, as well as access to primary data provided by the company to the author as the direct executor of the project to be carried out. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained from similar literature that had been previously created, including articles, journals, books, internet sites, and previous research related to the research being conducted.

Data collection techniques are methods used by researchers to capture or collect information or data according to the scope of the research (Wiratna, 2014). Data collection techniques need to be considered in research, because data collection is carried out to obtain data that is relevant to the problem being researched, so that problems that arise can be solved. The data collection techniques used in this research were carried out by means of observation, interviews, questionnaires and documentation studies. Meanwhile, data processing techniques were carried out using the Miles and Huberman model analysis technique. Miles and Huberman in Sugiyono (Sugiyono, 2017), state that qualitative data analysis techniques use interactive activities and continue continuously until they are finished or the data is saturated. This qualitative analysis activity consists of four stages, namely Data Collection, Data Reduction, Data Display, and Conclusion Drawing.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

❖ *Business Meeting Planning*

Effective business meetings will produce good decisions and optimal mutual agreements. However, a business meeting will not be effective if it is not well prepared or the planning stage is not optimal. The preparation referred to is not only technical preparation, but also substantial planning.

A. *Goal Setting*

At the stage of determining the objectives of a business meeting, objectives are determined consisting of objectives, framework and output for each agenda item that will be implemented. This activity aims to identify and clearly determine

the direction the company wants to achieve, both short, medium and long term. Having clear goals will help provide direction and provide a basis for further planning. The following are the objectives to be achieved from the 2023 Rahsa Nusantara business meeting activities:

- *To evaluate all achievements in last period*
- *To plan Rahsa Nusantara's strategic initiatives 2024*
- *Mapping current business ecosystem*
- *Planning metrics or targets*
- *Redesigning Rahsa Nusantara 2024*

Meanwhile, the expected outcomes from Rahsa Nusantara's business meeting activities include carrying out the process of identifying the potential and existing problems of each division in the past year, looking for common threads of problems, and reformulating the company's objectives in 2024, with output in the form of North Star Metric (NSM). This matrix will capture Rahsa Nusantara's core business values which will be conveyed to customers and will help the company to optimize current resources and direct efforts towards long-term success in 2024.

B. *Preparation of Program or Meeting Agenda*

The program preparation stage and determining the meeting agenda includes technical matters being prepared, and substantial matters in the form of determining the main topics to be discussed, as well as the time allocation for each agenda item. Technical matters that need to be prepared include:

- Determining the location by looking for business meeting venue options by considering the available facilities, and attaching these venue options to a deck.
- Creation of a Google Form for selecting a venue, determining transportation and accommodation, as well as selecting consumption for business meeting participants.
- Determination of a rough rundown based on the business meeting agenda.
- Search and determination of ice breaking games.
- Making a business meeting handbook containing descriptions, details of activities, objectives, place, agenda, pre-read material, equipment, room assignments, car assignments, as well as dress codes for business meeting activities.
- Communication and coordination with business meeting participants to provide information or determine participants' needs.
- Preparation of manpower to become Master of Ceremony, minutes, visual design, consumption PIC, and games PIC with other meeting committees.
- Preparation of budget and preparation of accommodation needs, tools, equipment, transportation, events and overall participant consumption.

C. *Trial or Simulation Method*

At this stage, two simulations have been carried out with the relevant divisions. The first simulation was carried out by applying one of the activity agendas using

the role playing method on the business meeting agenda, which was called Social Presencing Theater. Meanwhile, the second simulation was carried out by applying the discussion method to find out the grand strategy, which at that time discussed the Rahsa Nusantara Customer Journey. This trial or simulation is carried out to ensure the presentation equipment is working, understand the flow of the meeting, and ensure all related technical elements are running well.

D. Communication and Socialization

The planning stage also involves communication and outreach to the parties involved by explaining the information they need to know, so that business meeting activities can run effectively according to the expected goals. Communication and socialization activities for business meetings are carried out so that all parties involved have the same understanding and agreement, so that in their implementation there will be no internal obstacles due to misunderstandings and disagreements.

V. CONCLUSION

❖ Conclusions and Recommendations

PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara's business meeting planning has been carried out optimally in accordance with the theory and rules of effective meetings by carrying out several steps, namely setting goals, preparing a meeting program or agenda, testing or simulating methods, as well as communication and outreach to meeting participants. Overall, this business meeting has also succeeded in achieving the expected objectives, namely evaluating Rahsa Nusantara's achievements over the past year, formulating new goals to be achieved in the coming period, and designing strategies or innovations that will help Rahsa Nusantara achieve company success in the future. This project also received positive feedback which increased from the previous year from the views of participants and committee that needed to be improved. PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara's annual business project has been successfully implemented, marked by achieved objectives, positive feedback from participants, and more optimal method implementation. However, there is still room for improvement so that the next business meeting can be run more effectively.

According to the indicators for effective meetings presented by Reboni (2014), namely starting and finishing on time, setting an agenda or goal, and establishing basic rules for meeting implementation.

A. Active participants

A meeting can be said to be good if the participants in the meeting can play an active role in solving problems and are not passive during the meeting activities. Through the use of brainstorming methods, group discussions, role playing, and presentations which are applied to meeting activities, participants can be actively involved and not hesitate to give opinions.

B. Focus on the discussion

Debates during meetings are normal, but if the discussion has been going on for a long time and the discussion points have widened or are not in accordance with what is being discussed in the meeting, the discussion must immediately be directed back to the main topic of the meeting discussion.

C. Time discipline

Punctuality in meeting activities, such as the presence of meeting participants, suitability of the agenda time with the meeting rundown, as well as time contracts, or the end time of the meeting that has been agreed upon by the meeting leader and meeting participants need to be considered in the meeting implementation stages.

D. Conformity of planning with implementation

Concerns with the suitability of plans, goals, or policy objectives, clear and consistent methods. The suitability in question is first, the suitability between the implementation of the method and the needs of the participants. Second, the suitability between the implementation method and the implementation plan. Third, compatibility between the target participants and the implementing organization, namely the compatibility between the conditions decided by the implementing organization to obtain the output of the activity and what the participants do.

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